

Evaluation of IEM, Dubois and Oh Radar Backscatter Models using Airborne L-band SAR

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ABSTRACT

The backscatter predicted by three common surface scattering models (the Integral Equation Model - IEM, the Dubois, and the Oh models) was evaluated against fully-polarised L-band airborne observations. Before any site-specific calibration, the Oh model was found to be the most accurate amongst the three, with mean errors between simulated and observed backscatter of respectively 1.2 dB (± 2.6 dB standard deviation of the error) and -0.4 dB (± 2.4 dB) for HH and VV polarisation, while the IEM and Dubois presented larger errors, with a maximum of 4.5 dB (± 2 dB) for the IEM model in VV polarisation. The backscatter errors were observed to be related to surface roughness, another major factor determining the electromagnetic scattering at the soil surface. An existing semi-empirical calibration of the surface roughness correlation length was therefore applied to improve the mismatch between modeled and observed backscatters. The application of the semi-empirical calibration led to a significant improvement of the backscatter prediction for the IEM model. After calibration, the IEM model outperformed the Oh model, resulting in a mean backscatter error of respectively -0.3 dB (± 1.1 dB) and -0.2 (± 1.2 dB) for HH and VV polarisation. To test the robustness of the semi-empirical calibration, calibration functions derived from an independent data set were applied and shown to also improve the (uncalibrated) IEM model performance, suggesting that the calibration procedure is relatively robust for global application.

1. INTRODUCTION

Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) is a promising option for temporal monitoring of near-surface soil moisture at a spatial and temporal resolution suitable for hydrological and agricultural applications. The extraction of accurate soil moisture information from SAR data is subject to the accurate modeling of the relative contribution of soil moisture and surface roughness to the power backscattered at the soil surface. Among the numerous surface scattering models reported in the literature, the most widely applied are a physical model, the Integral Equation Model (IEM) developed in [1], and two semi-empirical models, the Dubois [2] and the Oh [3] models. Semi-empirical models provide relatively simple relationships between surface properties and SAR metrics that

reflect to a certain extent the physics of the scattering mechanisms. However they rely on parameters that are often site-specific and therefore valid only for specific soil conditions. Conversely, physical approaches are based on electromagnetic scattering theory and, even though they provide site-independent relationships, are mathematically more complex and involve a heavier computational burden.

Each of the models has been extensively tested in laboratory conditions and tower-mounted sensors [2, 4-7]. However, testing of such models using airborne or spaceborne SAR over natural and agricultural surfaces has been mainly focused on the previous generation of C-band SAR sensors such as RADARSAT and ERS [8-12]. Only a few studies have assessed the models individually using L-band data [13-16], and a direct inter-comparison of all three models with L-band multi-polarised data is currently lacking. Previous studies provided contrasting results on the accuracy of the individual models at L-band, with most reporting discrepancies between modeled and observed backscatter which can render soil moisture estimation using such models inaccurate. Only one study reported an unbiased agreement between IEM-simulated and observed backscatter at both polarisations [15]. Other studies have indicated a tendency of the IEM model to overestimate the L-band observed backscatters, by up to 3-5 dB for rough surfaces (surface Root Mean Square > 1 cm) [13]. Nevertheless, the IEM and Dubois models were generally found to be more accurate than earlier versions [6, 17] of the Oh model [14, 16]. Generally the uncertainty on surface roughness (including measurement error, multi-scale effects and spatial heterogeneity) has been addressed as a major factor in the failure of the models to reproduce the backscatters observed by airborne and spaceborne sensors [9, 13, 18].

The characterisation of surface roughness has been traditionally based on three parameters, namely the root mean square of the surface heights (hereby referred to as “surface rms”), the correlation length, and the shape of the Auto-Correlation Function (ACF) [18]. The empirical ACF is usually approximated using an exponential or Gaussian function. However, measuring the correlation length is a problematic task. Due the large spatial variability and multi-scale nature of natural and agricultural surfaces [19], surface roughness parameters estimated from field measurements are very sensitive to the length of the profile over which they are measured [20]. In order to overcome this problem, a few studies have proposed semi-empirical calibrations of the surface roughness correlation length [8, 9, 12, 21-23], the most difficult surface parameter to measure and characterize spatially, with considerable improvement in the performance of the model reported after semi-empirical calibration. The methodology proposed in those studies consists of replacing the measured correlation length by a semi-empirical fitting parameter (“ L_{opt} ”) which aims at compensating for measurement and model errors associated to the roughness correlation length. The fitting parameter was found to be linked to the surface roughness, increasing with increasing surface rms by either a linear, exponential or power calibration function, the exact relationship $L_{opt} = f(\text{rms})$ been dependent on the sensor incidence angle, polarisation, and frequency [9]. For a

fixed surface rms, L_{opt} was reported to decrease strongly with increasing incidence angle at both C-band [22] and X-band [23]. The variation of L_{opt} with sensor frequency changed depending upon the assumption made in the IEM model regarding the shape of the surface Autocorrelation Function (ACF), resulting in either a decrease (for Gaussian ACF) or increase (for exponential ACF) of L_{opt} with frequency increasing from L to X-band [22, 23]. Once appropriate equations for the fitting parameter L_{opt} are defined for a given sensor configuration, L_{opt} can be calculated for the known surface rms. The advantage of the procedure is that the number of surface parameters needed to characterize the backscatter is reduced from three (soil moisture, surface rms and correlation length) to two (soil moisture and surface rms). Equations for the fitting parameter L_{opt} have been reported to date for C-band [8, 9, 12, 22] and X-band [23]. However, to date limited attention has been devoted to estimating the fitting parameter for L-band data; Values for the fitting parameter L_{opt} were provided in [9] for L-band observations at HH polarisation and a limited range of incidence angles (44° - 57°), but no function was fitted. Alternative approaches have been proposed that calibrate both the surface rms and correlation length using linear regression functions dependent on the backscatter itself [24]. However, in this study the approach of [8, 9, 12, 22, 23] is preferred as it provides a set of functional relationships between the fitting parameters and the surface rms as a function incidence angle, polarisation and frequency, rather than a site-specific regression between effective roughness parameters and the SAR backscatter as in [24].

The objective of this study is to compare the accuracy of the backscatter simulated by the IEM, Dubois and Oh models for the first time using fully-polarised airborne L-band observations, and to assess the potential improvement of the model performance at L-band through semi-empirical calibration of the surface roughness parameters. To that end, first the impact of using roughness parameters associated with both the soil clods and tillage structure scales is analysed to select the most suitable roughness parameters. The performance of the three models is then compared 'as is', i.e., without applying any calibration. Possible causes of the mismatch between observed and simulated backscatter are then assessed and discussed. The semi-empirical calibration proposed by [8, 9, 12, 22, 23] is then applied to the models exhibiting the best performance (IEM and Oh), and the robustness of the calibration procedures is assessed and discussed.

2. STUDY AREA AND DATA SETS

The airborne and ground data used in this study were collected during the 3rd Soil Moisture Active Passive Experiment (SMAPEX-3), conducted from September 5-23, 2011, in the Yanco study area in south-eastern Australia [25]. The site is a semi-arid agricultural and grazing area located in the western plains of the Murrumbidgee catchment near the township of Yanco (Longitude $146^{\circ}10'$ E, Latitude $34^{\circ}50'$ S). The topography of the study area is flat with elevation ranging from 117 to 150m. Approximately one third of the area is characterised by intense irrigation activity. The principal summer crops grown are rice, corn, and soybeans,

while winter crops include wheat, barley, oats, and canola. Moderate rainfall in the first half of the experiment was followed by a dry-down period resulting in dry to intermediate soil moisture conditions ($0 - 0.2 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$), although for many irrigated fields higher values (up to $0.4 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$) were measured.

Surface backscatter measurements were acquired by the Polarimetric L-band Imaging Synthetic aperture radar (PLIS, [26]) on 9 dates (September 5th, 7th, 10th, 13th, 15th, 18th, 19th, 21st, 23rd), with coincident ground sampling of soil moisture. PLIS is a fully polarimetric, L-band (1.26 GHz) SAR sensor which illuminates the ground on either side of the aircraft at an incidence angle varying from 15° to 45° across the swath. Using a 30 MHz bandwidth, the single-look resolution is approximately 6 m (slant range) and 0.8 m (azimuth), which resulted in a ground-projected range resolution between 12 m (near range) – 8 m (far range). The PLIS mean ground swath is 2200m on both sides of the aircraft from an altitude of 3000m. PLIS polarimetric calibration was accomplished using a modified version of the distributed target method described in [27], using a distributed forest target in conjunction with six trihedral Passive Radar Calibrators (PRC). The polarimetrically calibrated data exhibited a mean ratio of the co-polarised channels of 1 and a mean phase difference of 3° and 6° respectively for left and right antenna. After radiometric calibration, the mean difference between the radar cross section observed over the six PRC's and the theoretical one was of 0.9 dB. This was calculated as the mean of the differences for all days and two daily calibration runs undertaken before and after scientific flights (absolute calibration accuracy). Such differences changed from day to day, and even changed sign between pre- and post-scientific flights calibration runs, making it unfeasible to further correct for such offsets even if only on a daily basis. The standard deviation of all offsets (relative calibration accuracy) was 0.8 dB.

Extensive ground sampling of near-surface (0-5 cm) soil moisture and surface roughness was conducted on rotation at approximately 80 agricultural fields, including several fields presenting bare surface conditions in preparation for the summer crops. Eleven such fields were selected for the purpose of this study. Although surface roughness was measured at 13 bare fields, two fields were excluded from the analysis as they either presented regular banks or were imaged at very steep angles which resulted in an elevated coherent backscatter component (approximately 9 dB higher than bare fields with similar surface roughness but without regular banks). Modeling the backscatter from such fields would require detailed knowledge of the geometry of the regular banks, which was not available. Table 1 lists the main characteristics of the fields used in this analysis. Soil moisture was monitored at each field on a weekly basis, therefore providing concurrent SAR observation and soil moisture validation data for three dates for each field. Soil moisture measurements were conducted using portable dielectric probes on a regular grid of locations equally spaced at 250m. At each sampling location 3 soil moisture measurements were taken within a 1 m radius and averaged to characterize small scale soil moisture variability. The dielectric probes were Stevens Water Hydraprobe® which

measure directly the complex soil dielectric constant with a cylindrical volume of soil of 5 cm in length bounded by the probe's 3 tines. The complex dielectric measurement were then converted to soil moisture (in m^3/m^3) using a calibration approach specifically developed and validated using hundreds of gravimetric samples collected in the study area, yielding an estimated accuracy of $0.035 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$ [28].

Surface roughness was measured once during the experiment at each field, using a custom-built surface profiler consisting of a 1-m long board with 200 pins spaced of 0.5 cm. A minimum of one and up to three measurements were taken within each field to characterize spatial variability in surface roughness. Each roughness measurement consisted of two, 3-m long surface profiles taken in the North-South and East-West directions, or alternatively in the direction parallel and perpendicular to the crop row directions if these were present. Surface rms and correlation length for each 3-m long profile were extracted from digital photos using the digital image processing MATLAB package QuiP [29]. The ground data collected are summarised in Table 1. A wide range of surface roughness conditions was analysed (1 – 7.6 cm).

On four of the fields analysed, activity of farming machinery was recorded during the observation period. This included mechanical alteration of the soil surface, such as ploughing or tillage. In such cases the surface roughness parameters, which were measured only once during the experiment, might not be representative of the surface conditions for all the dates considered. This is discussed in more detail in section 5.3. Other than the cases of farming activity, it can be safely assumed that roughness parameters were stable during the observation period given the absence of significant rainfall events.

3. SURFACE SCATTERING MODELS

Three surface models were considered for this analysis: A theoretical model, the Integral Equation Model (IEM) formulated in [1], and two semi-empirical models, one developed by Dubois et al. [2] and one proposed by Oh et al. [3]. These models are the most widely used for surface scattering simulation and are candidates for use in global soil moisture retrieval (for bare or low vegetated areas) due to their relatively simple structure and ease of inversion, and applicability to a wide range of soil moisture, surface roughness and incidence angles.

The IEM model is a theoretical backscattering model applicable to a wide range of roughness conditions. The complete mathematical formulation of the model is too lengthy to be included here but can be found in [1]. The model solves the integral equations for the tangential surface fields, taking into account the incidence angle, the surface rms and ACF (defined for a one-dimensional roughness profile) and the dielectric constant. A low frequency approximation of the IEM model was used in this study, valid in the region $k \cdot \text{rms} < 3$ (where k is the wave number $= 2\pi/\lambda$, where λ is the wavelength) in which single scattering

terms dominate over multiple scattering terms. Most agricultural surfaces, and all those listed in Table 1, fall within this validity domain. The IEM model simulations depend heavily on the assumption made concerning the shape (exponential or Gaussian) of the ACF. Several studies have found that for agricultural surfaces the exponential function provides the best results [9, 15].

Dubois et al. [2] developed a semi-empirical approach that expresses the radar backscatter coefficients as a function of incidence angle(θ), dielectric constant (ϵ_r), surface rms and wavelength as:

$$\sigma_{HH}^0 = 10^{-2.75} \left(\frac{\cos^{1.5}\theta}{\sin^5\theta} \right) 10^{0.028\epsilon_r \tan\theta} \lambda^{0.7} (k \text{ rms } \sin\theta)^{1.4} \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{VV}^0 = 10^{-2.35} \left(\frac{\cos^3\theta}{\sin^3\theta} \right) 10^{0.046\epsilon_r \tan\theta} \lambda^{0.7} (k \text{ rms } \sin\theta)^{1.1} \quad (2)$$

The algorithm is optimised for bare soils with $k^* \text{rms} < 2.5$, soil moisture $< 0.35 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$, and $\theta > 30^\circ$ [2].

The more commonly used version of the Oh model (hereby referred to as the “2002” version [3]), relates the co-polarised backscatter ratio p ($\sigma_{HH}^0/\sigma_{VV}^0$) and the cross-polarised ratio q ($\sigma_{HV}^0/\sigma_{VH}^0$) to the volumetric soil moisture (mv) as a function of incidence angle, wave number, surface rms and correlation length (L) as:

$$p = 1 - \left(\frac{\theta}{90^\circ} \right)^{0.35} mv^{-0.65} e^{-0.4(k \text{ rms})^{1.4}} \quad (3)$$

$$q = 0.1 \left(\frac{\text{rms}}{L} + \sin 1.3\theta \right)^{1.2} (1 - e^{-0.9(k \text{ rms})^{0.8}}) \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_{HV}^0 = 0.11 mv^{0.7} \cos^{2.2}\theta (1 - e^{-0.32(k \text{ rms})^{1.8}}). \quad (5)$$

The model is optimised within the soil moisture range $0.09 - 0.31 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$ and the roughness range $0.1 < k^* \text{rms} < 6$ [17]. Note that some of the fields listed in Table 1 are slightly outside such limits. However, in the case of semi-empirical models the validity domain is mostly associated to the range of the data range used for the parameterisation of the model, and therefore are to be taken as domains of “optimal performance” rather than “validity”.

Also note that the cross-polarised scattering is assumed to be negligible in the backscatter direction by the Dubois and IEM models. For this reason, and since the main objective of this paper is the comparison among the three models, the results presented are limited to the co-polarised channels (HH and VV).

4. METHODS

SAR observation and ground data were averaged within each field listed in Table 1 on each observation date. Between six and 18 soil moisture measurements were averaged for each field. The field-average backscattering coefficients were calculated by

averaging the linear (i.e., power units) single-look backscattering coefficients within the field boundaries, which were then converted to dB units through logarithmic conversion. Field-averaging of the geocoded single-look SAR data resulted in a negligible speckle noise (the number of looks per field ranged approximately between 123000 - 400000) with respect to the PLIS system radiometric accuracy which is ± 0.8 dB [25]. Since the Dubois and IEM models are formulated directly as a function of the dielectric constant, the temperature corrected dielectric measurements provided by the dielectric probes were used as input for these two models. The dielectric constant was converted to soil moisture prior to input to the Oh model using soil type specific calibration functions developed for the study area [28].

Given the presence of periodic row structure at several of the fields analysed (see Table 1), the performance of the models was assessed using two different options concerning the surface roughness parameters used as input to the models. In the first case it was assumed that the roughness scale relevant to the scattering is the fine scale (i.e., cm) associated with the soil clods and surface irregularities. In this case the roughness parameters used as input were those measured in the direction parallel to the crop row direction. This was done under the assumption that the fine-scale roughness component is isotropic, which is well supported by photogrammetric studies of various surfaces [30]. In the second case the coarser scale (i.e., 10's cm) roughness component associated with the periodic row structure was used as input for the model simulation. The parameters used in this case were those measured in the direction perpendicular to the crop rows. The two sets of input parameters are listed in Table 1. It should be noticed that for fields with no periodic row structure no distinction was made between the fine- and coarse-scale roughness components. In such cases the roughness parameters were taken as the average of those measured along the two cardinal directions.

The semi-empirical calibration of the scattering models was applied in this study following the technique proposed by [8] and further developed by [9, 12, 22, 23]. This was done in two stages: first models were calibrated using calibration functions $L_{opt} = f$ (rms) derived directly from the L-band data set used in this study. In the second stage the robustness of the semi-empirical calibration procedure was tested by applying calibration functions derived in previous studies [9, 22] to the present data set. The procedure adopted to calculate the calibration function $L_{opt} = f$ (rms) for the present L-band data set followed that described in [9]. The known field-averaged soil moisture and surface rms values were used together with the observed field-averaged backscatter to calculate the population of fitting parameters L_{opt} which minimize the difference between simulated and observed backscatter. A “bootstrap” re-sampling technique was then adopted in order to assign a measure of accuracy to the parameters of the fitting function. To that end 30 random re-sampling of the original data set were performed and a function $L_{opt} = f$ (rms) was fitted to each sub-sampled data set. Each of the 30 fitted functions was then applied to calibrate the IEM and Oh model and the “calibrated” backscatter error between simulated and observed backscatter was computed, together with the confidence intervals on such errors

associated to the 30 “bootstrap” re-sampling. In the second stage calibration functions derived in [9, 22] were applied to the present data set. Several calibration functions were proposed in those studies. However, most of these were derived from C-band SAR data (ERS and Radarsat). Given the strong dependence of the fitting parameter to sensor parameters (frequency, polarisation and incidence angle), ideally only fitting parameters derived from L-band data sets having the same configuration of the present data sets should be applied. Although no calibration function was provided for L-band data in any previous study, individual values of the fitting parameter L_{opt} were provided in [9] for L-band acquisitions (SIR-C sensor) in HH polarisation at 44° to 57° incidence angles. For the purpose of cross-comparison with the present study, a calibration function was therefore derived from such data set. Despite the incidence angle being different than that of the present data set (25°-38°, see Table 1), this calibration function was tested as it was the only other calibration function found in literature for L-band data sets, and as comparison with the calibration function derived in this study for L-band. Moreover, given the availability in [22] of comprehensive calibration functions for C-band and HH and VV polarisations, parameterised as a function of the incidence angle between 20° and 50°, such functions were also tested in this study to assess the robustness of calibration functions derived from the same sensor configuration in terms of incidence angle and polarization, but different sensor frequency. A summary of the calibration functions used in this study can be found in the results section in Table 4.

The performance of the scattering models in simulating the observed backscatter is evaluated throughout the manuscript using the mean and standard deviation of the error between simulated and observed backscatter across all dates as well as the correlation coefficient between simulated and observed backscatter (r and level of significance p factor). The mean error is a measure of the overall offset between simulation and observed variables, and can generally be attributed to systematic errors such as calibration offset or incorrect model parameterisation. Conversely, the standard deviation of the error quantifies the random component of the error associated to non-systematic factors (e.g., calibration and measurement noise, spatial heterogeneity of the input parameters).

5. RESULTS

5.1 Effect of Surface Roughness Parameterisation

Before comparing the three scattering models, the impact of using the fine- or coarse-scale component of the surface roughness profiles was assessed for all models using fields #14, 79 and 24. These fields were selected as they presented an anisotropic and periodic tillage structure and had not been subjected to farming activities during the experiment (Table 1), ensuring that the analysis was unaffected by changes in surface roughness occurring between the dates of ground measurements and SAR acquisitions. Results are presented in Table 2 for each model and roughness parameterisation (for the IEM model results are presented using

both exponential and Gaussian approximation of the ACF). When using coarse-scale roughness, all models presented mean backscatter errors ≥ 2 dB, with errors as high as 5 dB (IEM model in VV polarisation). The most accurate amongst the three models was the Oh model, with mean errors equal to 2 dB for HH and VV polarisations (and error standard deviation of respectively ± 1.7 dB and 2 dB). The use of the fine-scale roughness parameters resulted in a smaller offset between predicted and observed backscatters with respect to using the coarse-scale roughness, with a decrease of the mean error observed consistently across the three models and the two polarisations (except the IEM model using the Gaussian ACF). The improvement was stronger for the IEM and Dubois models (the mean error decreased respectively by up to 2dB and 3 dB). When using fine-scale roughness, all models were accurate to within 2 dB (with a maximum error standard deviation of ± 2.1 dB), the only exception being the IEM model (with exponential ACF) at VV polarisation, which presented a mean error of 4.5 dB (± 2.5 dB), although this was improved with respect to using the coarse-scale roughness (5.0 dB ± 1.9 dB). The Oh model was the most accurate of the three models even when using fine-scale roughness, with mean errors of -0.9 dB (± 1.9 dB) and -0.5 dB (± 2.1 dB) dB respectively for HH and VV polarisations, improved with respect to using the coarse-scale roughness of respectively 1.1 dB and 1.5 dB.

It is worth noting that, despite the larger offset between predicted and observed backscatter, the use of coarse-scale roughness led to slightly higher correlation coefficients and smaller error standard deviation between simulated and observed backscatter (for IEM exponential, Dubois and Oh model). This indicates the potential for a better fit of the models to observations were the significant biases to be removed. Nevertheless, in the following analysis the fine-scale roughness parameterisation was adopted since it was the one providing by far the smaller offsets between simulated and observed backscatter (Table 2). The mean backscatter errors for individual fields (not shown in Table 2) were higher for field #24 (mean errors between 4 – 7 dB for all models and polarisations) than for fields #14 and #79 (mean error < 5 dB). Note the field #24 was only one with tillage rows oriented at $\sim 50^\circ$ from the PLIS radar bore sight as opposed to 90° for fields #14 and #79 (Table 1), indicating potential effects of the tillage rows azimuthal direction on the model performance. The availability of only three fields with periodic structure does not allow a statistically significant analysis of this issue.

Results regarding the ACF shape effects on the IEM model showed that the exponential form led to a better match between predicted and observed backscatters when using fine-scale roughness for parameterisation, with a decrease in the mean backscatter error of as much as 2 dB, with respect to using the Gaussian ACF. When using the coarse-scale roughness parameterisation, although the exponential ACF resulted in slightly higher mean errors (by 0.5 and 0.9 dB respectively for HH and VV polarisation), it also led to significantly smaller error standard deviation and better correlation between predicted and observed backscatter. Consequently, it seems an exponential ACF is more appropriate, at least for the agricultural fields analysed, regardless of the roughness

parameterisation which is consistent with previous studies [9, 15, 17, 19]. The exponential ACF was therefore used in the analysis following.

5.2 Comparison between Uncalibrated Models

The performance of the IEM (with exponential ACF), Dubois and Oh models was then compared using data from all 11 fields listed in Table 1, using the fine-scale roughness parameterisation. The results are summarised in Table 3. Overall a reasonable agreement was observed between modeled and simulated backscatter for fields not farmed during the observation period. However, both the IEM and Dubois models were found to overestimate the observed backscatter. The Dubois model equally overestimated the HH and VV backscatter by approximately 1.8 dB (with an error standard deviation of respectively ± 2.5 dB and 2.3 dB). The IEM model performance was poorer for VV polarisation where the observed backscatter was overestimated by as much as 4.5 dB (± 2 dB), while at HH polarisation the performance of the IEM was similar to Dubois (1.8 dB overestimation ± 2.3 dB). The Oh model exhibited the smallest mean backscatter error amongst the three models, with limited underestimation of the observed backscatter (mean errors of -1.2 ± 2.6 dB and -0.4 ± 2.4 dB respectively for HH and VV). The skill of the Oh model with respect to the other two models was particularly significant in VV polarisation (> 1.3 dB improvement in mean error), while at HH polarisation the improvement was only a fraction of dB (0.6 dB). It should be noted, although not shown in Table 3, that all existing versions of the Oh model were tested: in this study (the “1992” [17], “1994”[6] and “2004”[7] versions along with the “2002” [3] version. Since the 2002 version provided by far the smaller mean error between observed and simulated backscatter it was the only one included in Table 3. By comparison, the following mean errors were obtained in HH polarisation (Oh 1992: -1.22 dB, Oh 1994: 2.1 dB, Oh 2004: -1.6 dB) and VV polarisation (Oh 1992: -0.4 dB, Oh 1994: 2.9 dB, Oh 2004: -0.8 dB).

Larger discrepancies between simulated and observed backscatter were obtained for three of the four fields where farming activity was observed (except field #43 in HH polarisation). Although this might be partially due to the fact that three of these fields (# 43, 51 and 70) have incidence angles ($< 30^\circ$) and soil moisture ($> 0.35 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$) slightly outside the validity domain for the Dubois and Oh model, the consistency of the backscatter error across three of the four fields for the IEM model (which have larger validity domains than the Dubois and Oh model) and the loss of correlation between predicted and observed backscatter (r decreasing from 0.5-0.7 for fields without farming activities to less than 0.4 for fields with farming activities) indicate this is likely the result of changes in surface roughness parameters having occurred between the date when the ground roughness measurements were taken and the SAR observations.

It is interesting to note that the IEM model, despite having a larger mean error than the Oh model, exhibited the highest correlation coefficient (0.7) as well as the smallest error standard deviation amongst the three models (2.3 dB and 2 dB respectively for HH and VV) for the non-farmed fields. This suggested that the IEM model had the potential to outperform the Oh model if the bias affecting it could be removed. This was further investigated in the next sections. It should also be noted that in the following analysis, field #87 was removed from the analysis. This field presented a backscatter (between approximately -7 and -8 dB) much higher than those of all other bare surfaces with comparable roughness conditions (-10 to -17dB), resulting in an underestimation of the observed backscatter by all models (see Table 3). Visual inspection of optical aerial images and ground inspection revealed that these elevated backscatter values were associated with the presence of regular steep banks (~1m high) bounding flooding rice bays within the paddock. Since such steep facets produce a strong coherent backscatter component which the models are not trained to simulate, the field was eliminated from subsequent analysis.

5.3 Dependence of the Uncalibrated Backscatter Error from Surface Conditions

Evaluation of scattering models conducted in previous studies has shown that a precise match between simulated and observed SAR backscatter is difficult to achieve. Even in the hypothetical absence of model error, errors deriving from surface roughness scale dependence and within-field variability, or inaccuracy of the in-situ measurements will introduce uncertainty. Similarly, scaling issues and within-field variability of soil moisture, as well as mismatches between the depths at which soil moisture is measured and the microwave effective penetration depth will affect the accuracy of scattering models.

In order to analyze the potential impact of the within-field spatial variability of surface roughness and soil moisture on the results presented in Table 3, the backscatter simulated by the three models when using field-averaged values of surface rms and correlation length ($\langle \text{rms} \rangle$ and $\langle L \rangle$) were compared with the backscatter simulated using the point-scale surface roughness measurements within each field when taken individually as input to the forward model. Similarly the backscatter simulated using the field-averaged soil moisture ($\langle \text{SM} \rangle$) was compared with that simulated using the individual soil moisture measurements within the field. The analysis was restricted to fields with at least 3 surface roughness measurements within the field boundaries, resulting in five fields with field-averaged conditions ranging from 1.4 – 4.4 cm ($\langle \text{rms} \rangle$), 8 – 26 cm ($\langle L \rangle$) and 0.05 – 0.25 m³/m³ ($\langle \text{SM} \rangle$). Histograms of the resulting backscatter differences are displayed in Figure 1, with mean differences and 95% confidence intervals also indicated for each model and polarisation combination. Although a large error variability was observed (up to 10 dB), the difference between backscatter simulated using individual and field-averaged measurements was between -1.8 and 0.3 dB (within 95% confidence interval). The impact of the heterogeneity on surface roughness (rms and L) appeared stronger than that of soil moisture for all models, although this might be partially due to the fewest number of surface roughness measurements available, as

indicated by the wider confidence intervals of the probability distribution for surface roughness heterogeneity (top panels in Figure 1). Interestingly, the Dubois model was less impacted by heterogeneity of both surface roughness and soil moisture than the IEM and Oh models. When comparing mean differences in Figure 1 with the mean simulation errors in Table 3, it can be observed that only in the case of the Oh model the combined uncertainty due to heterogeneity of surface roughness and soil moisture was roughly consistent (in magnitude and sign and taking into account the confidence intervals) to the mean backscatter error. This was not the case for the IEM and Dubois model, and particularly the IEM in VV polarisation, indicating that additional sources of uncertainty are affecting the backscatter errors in Table 3.

To understand whether the magnitude of the backscatter errors observed is associated to the magnitude of surface roughness (as opposed to its spatial variation), the field-averaged backscatter errors of Table 3 are plotted against the field-averaged surface rms and correlation length in Figure 2. Given the limited number of data points, the determination coefficient adjusted for sample size (r^2_{adj}) was used in this case instead of the correlation coefficient. It should be noted that the relatively narrow soil moisture dynamic range experienced during the SMAPEX-3 experiment and the limited incidence angle range of the fields characterised by bare conditions did not allow analysis of the dependence of the error on the field-average soil moisture and radar incidence angle. Despite the limited number of data points, the backscatter errors exhibited correlation with both the surface rms and correlation length. In HH polarisation both the IEM and Dubois model errors were correlated with both roughness parameters ($r^2_{adj} = 0.6 - 0.7$ with $p < 0.05$). Conversely, in VV polarisation, only the Dubois model maintained a significant correlation with both roughness parameters ($r^2_{adj} = 0.6 - 0.7$, $p < 0.05$), while the IEM model error was well correlated with the surface rms but poorly correlated with the correlation length (r^2_{adj} respectively 0.5 and 0.3, $p < 0.05$). The backscatter error is seen to increase with increasing surface rms for the IEM and Dubois models, with errors within ± 2 dB for surface rms up to 2.5 cm (except for IEM at VV polarisation which exhibits a strong bias as commented earlier) and then increased up to $\sim 5-7$ dB for surface rms values of ~ 5 cm. The Oh model, despite having small mean errors as seen in the previous section, exhibited some correlation with the surface roughness parameters, particularly for VV polarisation ($r^2_{adj} = 0.6$, $p < 0.05$). However, the Oh model provided a better match to the observed backscatter for rough surfaces (rms > 3 cm).

Several previous studies have analysed the reliability of surface roughness measurements carried out with manual profiles, indicating that the values obtained are highly variable and depend on the length of the profile used [18]. It has even been suggested that profiles as long as 40-200 times the correlation length might be needed to estimate surface rms and correlation length accurately [31]. Since both the IEM and Oh model simulate the impact of the correlation length in their original formulation, the observed correlation of the model error to the ground-measured surface roughness parameters could reflect the inherent uncertainty

in the measurement process for rough surfaces with larger correlation lengths, where the limited length of the profile used to characterize the surface roughness parameters becomes a limitation. In the next section a semi-empirical calibration of the correlation length is applied to investigate potential improvement of the mismatch with SAR data observed.

5.4 Semi-Empirical Calibration of the Scattering Models

The semi-empirical calibration procedure proposed in [8] and further developed in [9, 12, 22, 23] was applied in this study to assess potential improvement of the mismatch between observed and simulated backscatter observed in previous sections. This was motivated firstly by the observed correlation between model errors and surfaces with elevated roughness (section 5.3), and secondly by the fact that the IEM model, despite presenting significant offset between simulated and observed backscatter, also exhibited the highest correlation coefficient and smaller error standard deviation amongst the three models (see Table 3), indicating the potential for an improved backscatter prediction after removal of such biases. The semi-empirical calibration was applied in this study only to the IEM and Oh models since, in its original formulation, the Dubois model was parameterised only as a function of soil moisture and surface rms, therefore not allowing for correlation length calibration.

Since the semi-empirical calibration has not been applied before to L-band SAR data, it was necessary to first determine a suitable calibration function for each polarisation. The fitting procedure was described in detail in the methodology section 4, and the resulting calibration functions are shown in Figure 3. It should be noted that calibration functions were calculated and applied individually to the IEM and Oh model. This is because, as explained in [9, 22], the fitting parameter L_{opt} is not a “corrected” correlation length but rather it is to be regarded as a calibration coefficient, and is therefore specific to each model. With the present L-band data set an exponential function was found to be the best fit for the fitting parameter L_{opt} of the IEM model, whereas a power function was more suitable for the Oh model. However it should be noted that the determination coefficients of the various functions explored (exponential, power, linear and 2nd polynomial) were very similar and all in excess of 0.8. Not surprisingly, given the small range of incidence angle of the available data (30°-38° excluding field #87, see Table 1), L_{opt} was not seen to vary significantly with incidence angle. The fitted functions were quite similar for the two co-polarised channels for the Oh model, while for the IEM model, the calibrated L_{opt} for VV polarisation was higher than that for HH polarisation. In Table 4 the error in simulated backscatter by the IEM and Oh model after semi-empirical calibration are compared with the performance of the uncalibrated models (from Table 3 less the eliminated field #87), for the case of fields without activity of farming machinery. For the IEM model, the calibration was able to correct the offsets a between observed and simulated backscatter which affected the uncalibrated model, in particular bringing the mean backscatter error in VV polarisation from 4.9 dB to -0.7 dB. Moreover, the correlation coefficients and error standard deviation were improved for both polarisations, indicating the ability of the calibration to

compensate not only for systematic differences but also for random sources of error. For the Oh model, the calibration did not improve the model performance, with mean backscatter errors similar to the uncalibrated case, and generally poorer correlation and larger error standard deviation than the IEM model. After semi-empirical calibration, the IEM model outperformed the Oh model (both uncalibrated and calibrated) with respect to all the error metrics analysed.

The gray curves shown in Figure 3 represent the calibration functions fitted to the 30 sub-sampled data sets (using bootstrap). The narrow range of calibration curves indicates a good reliability of the exponential functions fitted, despite the limited data set. As a result of this, the confidence intervals on the error metrics shown in Table 4 (which are derived from applying the 30 individual calibration functions), are fairly narrow, providing confidence that the improvement of the error metrics with respect to the uncalibrated models is statistically significant. Figure 3 also displays the L-band and C-band calibration functions derived respectively from [9] and [22], and used to independently evaluate the findings of this study. Since the C-band calibration functions were provided in [22] as a function of the incidence angle, in Figure 3 the functions calculated for the minimum (30°) and maximum (38°) incidence angle of the present data set are shown (calibration curves for the intervening range 31° - 37° will lie between these two reference curves). The function derived for L-band, HH polarisation and 44° - 57° incidence angle (L-HH-44-57) was slightly lower than the fitting parameters calculated with the present data sets, which it followed reasonably well until surface rms ~ 3.5 cm. For higher values of surface rms the L-HH-44-57 underestimated the fitting parameters calibrated in this study. This is consistent with the decrease of fitting parameter with increasing incidence angle reported by [9, 22]. Despite the difference in frequency the C-band calibration functions matched reasonably well the fitting parameters calculated with the present data set for HH polarisation, while at VV polarisation the L-band fitting parameters were significantly underestimated by the C-band calibration functions. This was a result of the fact that at L-band the fitting parameters for VV polarisation were higher than those for HH polarisation, whereas the opposite was found in [22] for C-band.

Results of the independent calibration of the IEM using the L-HH-44-57 calibration function and the C-band calibration functions are presented in Table 4. It should be noted that L-HH-44-57 function was applied only to the HH data set as no calibration function was provided in [9] for VV polarisation. Moreover, the C-band functions from [22] were applied by using the exact incidence angle available for each SAR observation (see Table 4). Notably, both functions led to an improvement of the performance of the IEM model with respect to the uncalibrated case. In particular, the use of L-HH-44-57 decreased the mean backscatter error from 2.3 dB to 1 dB for HH polarisation. The use of C-band calibration functions also significantly improved the performance of the IEM for in both HH and VV polarisations, with a decrease in mean backscatter error from 2.3 dB to -0.9 dB (HH) and from 4.9 dB to 0.5 dB (VV). When compared to the performance of the Oh model, the IEM model calibrated using the

independent L- and C-band calibration functions outperformed the Oh model with higher correlation coefficients, smaller error standard deviation, and comparable mean errors .

6. DISCUSSION

In this study a refined version of the Oh model [3] was tested and found to outperform both the IEM and Dubois models in both HH and VV polarisations for a large range of surface roughness conditions (1.0-7.6 cm) and prior to any local re-calibration. The skill of the Oh model with respect to the IEM and Dubois models was particularly significant at VV polarisation, for which the IEM model overestimated the observed backscatter by up to 4.5dB. Consistently with previous studies, the performance of the IEM and Dubois models were found to be associated to surface roughness, with larger backscatter errors associated to rougher surface conditions ($rms > 2.5$ cm). Conversely, the Oh model was more robust across the range of roughness conditions analysed. This indicate that, before any calibration was applied, the application of the Oh model would result in the smallest overall offset between simulated and observed backscatters amongst the three models. This is in contrast with previous studies which indicated that the Oh model has higher offsets than either the IEM or the Dubois models at L-band [14, 16]. Both studies nevertheless dealt with previous versions of the Oh model [17], which was in this study observed to be less accurate than the most recent version. However, despite the discrepancies on the offset magnitude for the various models, this study agrees with the analysis done at L-band of in [14], [16] and [13] regarding the sign of these offsets: positive (overestimation) for IEM and Dubois, and negative (underestimation) for the Oh model.

The comparison between the models performed at L-band in the this study are consistent with previous analysis undertaken at C-band [10, 16, 32, 33] in that the IEM model predicted higher backscatters than the Oh model. However, the comparison with observed backscatters at C-band overall indicated better accuracy of the IEM model over the Oh model at such frequency [16, 32, 33], particularly over smooth surfaces, in contrast with what found in this study. Moreover, analysis of multi-polarised C-band data in [10] indicated that the IEM model correctly reflects the observed backscatter at VV polarisation, but it has a tendency to overestimate the observed backscatter at HH polarisation (2.9 dB). In this study the opposite was found for L-band, with the IEM exhibiting a stronger overestimation of the observed backscatter at VV polarisation (4.5 dB) than at HH polarisation (1.8 dB). Whether this is an effective deficiency of the IEM model at L-band and VV polarisation or rather a problem associated to instrumental error is an issue that requires confirmation using independent L-band data sets. In regards to the changes in model performance with increasing roughness, the resulted presented in this study for L-band agree well with observations done at C-band in that the IEM model is more affected by increasing surface roughness, with a tendency to overestimation for rough surfaces and to underestimation for smooth surfaces, while the Oh model is more robust across the roughness range typical of agricultural areas

[10, 16, 32, 33]. Therefore our conclusions are that at L-band the Oh model is a better choice when no calibration is performed, as it provides a smaller mean error between simulated and observed backscatter and is also more robust with respect to increases in surface roughness.

It is also worth noting that discrepancies in results between this and previous studies in regard to the performance of the various models might also depend on other factors, including the different surface conditions (soil moisture) and sensor characteristics (incidence angle). Consequently, the results presented are limited to relatively narrow range of incidence angles (24° - 38°) and soil moisture ($0.05 - 0.39 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$). Variations in the quality of the absolute calibration between SAR data sets might also result in discrepancies when applying the same model. It should be noted that the calibration accuracy of the SAR data used in this study was $\pm 0.9 \text{ dB}$ compared to $\pm 1-2 \text{ dB}$ used in the previous studies [13, 14].

Despite the better accuracy of the uncalibrated Oh model in terms of mean error, it was noted that the uncalibrated IEM model exhibited higher correlation coefficient and smaller error standard deviation. In modeling of physical systems, such improved error metrics are generally symptomatic of a more physically-sound response of the model to changing input parameters (in this case soil moisture and surface roughness). Analysis of possible sources of uncertainty in the modeled backscatter, namely the within-field variability of surface roughness and soil moisture, indicated that these are unlikely the cause of the offset observed for the uncalibrated IEM model, since they did not match in either magnitude nor sign the mismatch between simulated and observed backscatters. It was in fact observed that both the spatial variability in surface roughness and soil moisture would tend to result in an underestimation of the field-averaged backscatter, rather than an overestimation as generally observed in Table 3.

The application of the semi-empirical calibration of the correlation length performed in this study is the first independent verification of the procedure for L-band data at both HH and VV polarisations. As reported in previous studies [8, 9, 12, 22, 23], the fitting parameter L_{opt} was found to be linked to the surface rms. In this study an exponential function was found to be more suitable to model such dependency for the IEM model instead of the power function proposed in [9, 22]. After semi-empirical calibration, the IEM outperformed the Oh model with respect to all the error metrics analysed. It is important to notice that additional sources of uncertainty, not specifically analysed here, could affect the comparison between SAR observed and modeled backscatter. These include measurement error of the dielectric probes used for soil monitoring as well as mismatch between the depth at which soil moisture is measured and the microwave effective penetration depth. The latter in particular might well result in a significant offset between modeled and observed backscatter. Therefore, one potential caveat of the analysis presented (already noted in [9]) is that the semi-empirical calibration might just be absorbing whatever sources of uncertainty affect the mismatch between observed and simulated backscatter. However, the observed relationship between L_{opt} and surface rms, confirmed in this

study, is a good indicator that the calibration parameter is likely to yield a physical meaning which can be exploited to derive a unique $L_{opt} = f(\text{rms})$ law for each sensor configuration.

For the semi-empirical calibration of the surface roughness correlation length to be valuable to global application, the fitting function should be robust, at least for a given sensor configuration (frequency, incidence angle and polarisation). Although no calibration functions were available in literature for L-band data at the same incidence angle analysed in this study, a good match between simulated and observed backscatter was achieved using calibration functions derived for different configurations, one for similar incidence angles but different SAR frequency (C-band vs. L-band) and the other for the same frequency but different incidence angle range (30° - 38° vs. 44° - 57°). Both calibration functions improved the performance of the uncalibrated IEM model. Additionally, the calibrated IEM model was more accurate than the Oh model (better error standard deviation and correlation coefficient and similar mean error).

Therefore a significant outcome of this study is that it confirmed the robustness of the calibration procedures at L-band between different data sets. In particular, the differences between the calibration functions derived in this study and that derived from [9] for L-band and HH polarisation is consistent with the decrease of fitting parameter L_{opt} with increasing incidence angle reported in [9] and [22]. The similarity between the L-band calibration functions derived in this study for HH polarisation and the C-band functions proposed by [22] for the same incidence angles and polarisation is also encouraging for global application of the calibration procedure. Such similarity is consistent with the observation that changes of the calibration parameters between frequencies are of smaller magnitude relatively to those associated with changes in incidence angle, for the range of configurations useful for remote sensing of soil moisture using SAR [9]. For example, as observed in [9] for a 4 cm surface rms, the C-band L_{opt} varied from 200 cm to 50 cm when going from 21° incidence angle to $\sim 40^\circ$, but it only changed between 30cm and 60cm between C-band and L-band at 57° . It should be noted that the similarity between the L-band calibration functions derived in this study and the C-band functions proposed by [22] for the same incidence angles did not hold at VV polarisation. However, this is a consequence of the low accuracy of the IEM model which was affected by high overestimation errors at VV polarisation in L-band (4.5 dB mean error, see section 5.2), while results reported in [22] for similar incidence angles showed much smaller biases in VV polarisation at C-band (1.4 dB). Conversely, at HH polarisation the IEM performance was similar at L- (1.8 dB) and C-band (2.4 dB), hence the similarity between the L- and C-band calibration functions for HH polarisation. The result presented therefore support the viability of a unified calibration function, provided a relationship between L_{opt} and surface rms is available for the particular frequency, polarisation and incidence angle, which could be applied at global scale to improve the performance of the IEM without the need for local re-calibration.

The Dubois model presented significant backscatter errors which could not be corrected through the same calibration procedure applied to the IEM and Oh models. Since the Dubois model does not simulate the effect of the correlation length, improvement of the model performance would require a modification of the original model parameters, to fit the local conditions. This was not considered a valuable exercise toward global application of SAR scattering models, since it would certainly improve the performance of the model, but most likely only for the local conditions. Conversely, the semi-empirical calibration adopted for the IEM and Oh models has the advantage of not modifying the model structure, but rather establishing an empirical relationship between roughness parameters (or at least their inter-dependence with respect to determining the surface scattering) which might turn out to be physically justifiable, and therefore generally applicable.

The analysis on the impact of using different roughness parameters could also explain discrepancies between the observed accuracy of the various scattering models in different studies. Previous studies are not always clear on how the information from the ground profiles is used, but it is common practice in surface scattering studies to use the surface rms as calculated over the raw profile (i.e., no distinction of roughness scales). The results from this study indicate that, in the presence of anisotropic tillage structure, an improved backscatter prediction for the IEM and Dubois models can be obtained when using the fine-scale roughness component associated with the soil clods and surface irregularities.

The comparison between modeled and observed backscatter was also observed to be strongly degraded on fields subjected to farming activities, due to by changes in surface roughness occurring between the date when the ground roughness measurements were taken and the SAR observations. The information on farming dates received from the local farmers was not accurate enough (temporally) to allow improving the analysis for these fields. However, these results do highlight the strong impact of the assumption of temporal stability of surface roughness parameters which is frequently made in SAR-based soil moisture retrieval. The mean backscatter error over farmed fields was between 3 and 3.7dB higher than over non-farmed fields for the IEM and Dubois model. The accuracy of the Oh model was less impacted by the farming activities in terms of mean error (the mean error was similar to that for the non-farmed fields), although these resulted in a positive bias (overestimation), particularly in VV polarisation, and a significantly lower correlation coefficient.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Three common surface scattering models were tested using airborne L-band multi-polarised SAR data. The performance of the models was assessed both using surface roughness parameters measured by ground profile as well as those derived from a semi-empirical calibration procedure. The major findings of this study can be summarised as follows:

- Comparison between uncalibrated models: Before calibration, the Oh model (2002 version) exhibited the best agreement between simulated and observed backscatter, with a mean error between model-simulated and SAR-observed backscatter of -1.2 dB (± 2.6 dB error standard deviation) and -0.4 dB (± 2.4 dB) respectively for HH and VV polarisations. Larger backscatter errors were observed for the IEM model, with mean errors of respectively 1.8 dB (± 2.3 dB) and 4.5 dB (± 2 dB) for HH and VV, and for the Dubois model, with mean errors of respectively 1.8 dB (± 2.5 dB) and 1.7 dB (± 2.3 dB). The skill of the Oh model with respect to the remaining models was particularly significant in VV polarisation, where the IEM model presented the highest errors. This observation warrants further analysis to establish whether this is an effective deficiency of the IEM model at L-band and VV polarisation or rather a problem associated to instrumental error;
- Impact of the field-scale variability of soil moisture and roughness parameters: This was quantified to be between -1.8 and 0.3 dB, the impact of the heterogeneity on surface roughness rms and correlation length being stronger than that of soil moisture for all models. However, such sources of errors did not fully explain model inaccuracies, in particular the large overestimation of the observed backscatter by the IEM model at VV polarisation;
- Dependence of the uncalibrated model error on surface roughness conditions: The elevated backscatter errors for the IEM model were found to be associated to rough surface conditions, with a mean error < 2 dB for smooth surface conditions (rms < 2.5 cm) but increasing up to ~ 5 -7 dB for surface rms values of ~ 5 cm. Poorer backscatter predictions were obtained when using the coarse-scale roughness component associated with the tillage structure, with an increase in backscatter mean error between 2-3 dB (for HH polarisation) and 0.5-2.5 dB (VV) with respect to the use of the fine-scale roughness component (i.e., associated with the soil clods and surface irregularities).
- Model accuracy after semi-empirical calibration: The application of an existing semi-empirical calibration of the surface roughness correlation length led to a significant improvement in the performance of the IEM model. After calibration, the IEM model outperformed the Oh model, not only reducing the overall backscatter error to -0.3 dB (± 1.1 dB) and -0.2 dB (± 1.2 dB) respectively for HH and VV polarisation but also presenting significantly higher correlation between simulated and observed backscatter. The semi-empirical fitting parameter was found to be related to the surface rms through an exponential function.
- IEM Semi-empirical calibration for L-band SAR observations: Two exponential semi-empirical calibration functions applicable to the IEM model were fitted and tested. The calibration functions, applicable to L-band data in the 30-38° incidence angle range and respectively HH and VV polarization, complements similar calibration functions provided in [22] for C-band data. The analysis presented warrants further investigation using L-band observations at a wider range of

incidence angle, in order to derive specific calibration functions for the IEM for a variety of L-band configurations (polarisation and incidence angle) relevant to future L-band SAR missions with ScanSAR capabilities;

- Robustness of the semi-empirical calibration procedure: The fitting parameter derived in this study for L-band and HH – polarisation at 30-38° incidence angles was lower than that derived from an independent data set in [9] at the same configuration but higher incidence angles (44-57°), consistently with observations previously done at C-band on the decrease of the fitting parameter with increasing incidence angle. The calibration functions derived in [22] for the same incidence angles but different frequency (C-band) matched well the fitting parameters calculated in this study for HH polarization. Significant differences between the VV-polarised calibration curves at L- and C-band were instead observed, as a consequence of the inaccuracies of the IEM model in VV polarization at L-band. Nevertheless, the independent calibration functions in both frequencies were shown to improve the performance of the uncalibrated IEM model at L-band, despite differences in frequency or incidence angles, suggesting that the calibration procedure is relatively robust and yields potential for future global application.

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Table 1. Characteristics of the bare agricultural fields and summary of the ground data collected. For fields with periodic structure the row azimuth angle is given. Superscripts in the “field #” column indicate fields without (*) and with (+) activity of farming machinery recorded during the observation period. The surface roughness parameters indicated are the surface heights root mean square (rms) and correlation length (L)

Field #	SAR Inc. Angle	Row Azimuth Angle	Soil Moisture min-max [m ³ /m ³]	Surface Roughness [cm]			
				Fine-scale (along rows)		Coarse-scale (across rows)	
				rms	L	rms	L
87*	35°	-	0.12-0.18	3.7	9.1	3.7	9.1
48*	38°	-	0.09-0.12	3.3	15.5	3.3	15.5
49*	35°	-	0.08-0.10	4.6	20.8	4.6	20.8
50*	30°	-	0.07-0.16	2.1	9.3	2.1	9.3
14*	38°	10°	0.05-0.09	2.3	7.2	6.0	18.9
79*	31°	10°	0.05-0.13	1.0	6.9	1.3	10.6
24*	38°	140°	0.25-0.27	3.3	11.0	5.1	30.8
1 ⁺	36°	80°	0.14-0.19	2.3	8.0	6.4	23.0
43 ⁺	24°	20°	0.09-0.39	1.1	2.6	6.6	22.3
51 ⁺	24°	110°	0.07-0.38	1.5	10.8	7.6	23.6
70 ⁺	25°	10°	0.12-0.25	1.7	5.7	5.7	22.5

Table 2. Impact of different roughness parameterisation on the backscatter simulation error using the IEM, Dubois and Oh models. For the IEM, results are shown using both an exponential and Gaussian assumption concerning the shape of the surface roughness auto-correlation function. For each polarisation the mean (\pm standard deviation, σ) of the error and correlation coefficient (r) between simulated and observed backscatter are shown. All r values are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) except those indicated with (*)

Model	Roughness parameteriz. (Nr.pts)	HH-pol		VV-pol	
		Mean error (\pm st.dev.)	r	Mean error (\pm st.dev.)	r
IEM (exp.)	Fine (8)	1.9 (\pm 2.1)	0.7	4.5 (\pm 2.5)	0.8
	Coarse (8)	3.9 (\pm 2.1)	0.9	5.0 (\pm 1.9)	0.8
IEM (gaus.)	Fine (8)	4.6 (\pm 1.9)	0.7	7.1 (\pm 2.1)	0.8
	Coarse (8)	3.4 (\pm 2.7)	-0.2(*)	4.1 (\pm 3.6)	0.1(*)
Dubois	Fine (8)	1.8 (\pm 2.0)	0.5	1.8 (\pm 2.3)	0.7
	Coarse (8)	4.8 (\pm 1.9)	0.9	4.2 (\pm 2.2)	0.9
Oh (2002)	Fine (8)	-0.9 (\pm 1.9)	0.5	-0.5 (\pm 2.1)	0.6
	Coarse (8)	2.0 (\pm 1.7)	0.8	2.0 (\pm 2.0)	0.9

Table 3. Comparison between the backscatter simulated by the IEM (with exponential ACF), Dubois and Oh models and that measured by the airborne SAR. For individual fields, only the mean error between simulated and observed backscatter is shown. Cumulated statistics for fields without (*) and with (+) activity of farming machinery are then shown as the mean (and standard deviation σ) of the error as well as the correlation coefficient (r) between simulated and observed backscatter. The best simulations for each field and polarisation are highlighted in bold. All values are in Decibels. All r values are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) except those indicated by (**).

Field# (Nr.pts)	HH - pol			VV - pol		
	<i>IEM</i>	<i>Dubois</i>	<i>Oh (2002)</i>	<i>IEM</i>	<i>Dubois</i>	<i>Oh (2002)</i>
87*(3)	-1.1	-1.5	-5.0	2.3	-1.3	-3.7
48*(3)	2.7	2.7	0.1	5.0	2.3	0.5
49*(3)	4.9	5.6	2.2	6.5	4.8	2.8
50*(3)	0.7	0.4	-2.9	4.3	1.0	-1.1
14*(2)	0.2	-0.6	-3.6	3.8	-0.4	-3.0
79*(3)	0.6	1.2	-0.7	2.4	0.7	-1.0
24*(3)	4.3	3.9	0.8	7.1	4.3	1.6
All*(20)						
Mean (σ)	1.8 (2.3)	1.8 (2.5)	-1.2 (2.6)	4.5 (2.0)	1.7 (2.3)	-0.4 (2.4)
r	0.7	0.6	0.5	0.7	0.6	0.6
1+(3)	5.9	4.6	2.1	8.6	4.1	2.2
43+(3)	0.6	4.0	-1.7	3.8	4.4	0.5
51+(3)	7.2	7.5	3.0	9.8	7.1	4.7
70+(3)	5.6	5.8	1.0	7.9	4.6	1.9
All+(12)	4.8	5.5	1.1	7.5	5.0	2.3
Mean (σ)	4.8 (2.8)	5.5 (1.8)	1.1 (2.1)	7.5 (2.7)	5.0 (1.9)	2.3 (2.1)
r	0.04**	0.4**	0.1**	0.2**	0.2**	0.2**

Table 4. Comparison between the backscatter simulated by the IEM and Oh models and that measured by the airborne SAR before and after semi-empirical calibration. Calibration results are presented using different calibration equations: (i) those developed in this study, (ii) that derived in this study from L-band data at HH-polarisation and 44°-57° presented in [9], and (iii) those proposed by [22] for C-band, HH- and VV-polarisation as a function of the incidence angle. The mean and standard deviation of the error and the correlation coefficient (r) are shown for each case. For data calibrated in this study, the 95% confidence intervals associated to 30 bootstrap sampling cases during calibration are reported (\pm). Only fields without activity of farming machinery were included. Field #87 was excluded from the analysis as explained in the text. All values are in decibels except for the correlation coefficient r. All r values are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Values of the coefficients in [22] are: $\delta_{HH} = 4.026$, $\delta_{VV} = 3.289$, $\mu_{HH} = \mu_{VV} = -1.744$, $\eta_{HH} = \eta_{VV} = -0.0025$, $\varepsilon_{HH} = 1.551$, $\varepsilon_{VV} = 1.222$.

	Calibration equation Lopt (band, polarisation, angle)	HH - pol			VV - pol		
		Mean	St.dev.	r	Mean	St.dev.	r
IEM							
Uncalibrated	<i>none</i>	2.3	2.0	0.7	4.9	1.9	0.8
Calibrated [This study]	$L_{opt}(L, HH, 30-38^\circ) = 3.897 * \exp(0.765 * rms)$ $L_{opt}(L, VV, 30-38^\circ) = 11.97 * \exp(0.578 * rms)$	-0.3 \pm 0.1	1.1 \pm 0.02	0.8 \pm 0.01	-0.2 \pm 0.1	1.2 \pm 0.02	0.8 \pm 0.01
Calibrated using [9]	$L_{opt}(L, HH, 44-57^\circ) = 2.298 * rms^{(2.081)}$	1.0	1.9	0.8	N/A	N/A	N/A
Calibrated using [22]	$L_{opt}(C) = \delta_{PP}(\sin\theta)^{\mu_{PP}} * rms^{(\eta_{PP}\theta + \varepsilon_{PP})}$	-0.9	1.8	0.6	0.5	2.0	0.7
Oh (2002)							
Uncalibrated	<i>none</i>	-0.5	2.1	0.5	0.1	2.0	0.6
Calibrated [This study]	$L_{opt}(L, HH, 30-38^\circ) = 6.644 * rms^{(0.848)}$ $L_{opt}(L, VV, 30-38^\circ) = 5.845 * rms^{(0.964)}$	0.7 \pm 0.2	2.2 \pm 0.1	0.3 \pm 0.06	0.3 \pm 0.2	1.6 \pm 0.1	0.5 \pm 0.05

Figure 1. Impact of within-field spatial variability of surface roughness (top panels) and soil moisture (bottom panel) on the performance of the IEM, Dubois and Oh scattering models. Surface parameters considered are roughness Root Mean Square (rms), correlation length (L) and soil moisture (SM). The histograms indicate differences between backscatter simulated (σ_{SIM}) using the point-scale measurements and the field-averaged values for each parameter ($\langle \rangle$), with all other parameters set to the field-averaged value. Numbers indicate the mean difference for each model and polarisation (\pm 95% confidence interval). The field-averaged conditions of the data presented range from 1.4 – 4.4 cm ($\langle rms \rangle$), 8 – 26 cm ($\langle L \rangle$) and 0.05 – 0.25 m³/m³ ($\langle SM \rangle$)

Figure 2. Dependence of the error between model-simulated and SAR-observed backscatter from the field-averaged surface roughness Root Mean Square (top row) and the correlation length (bottom row) for HH (left panels) and VV (right panels) polarisations. The determination coefficient (adjusted for the sample size) is shown in the legend for each case. All correlation coefficients are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Only fields not subjected to farming activities during the observation period are included in this plot.

Figure 3. Semi-empirical calibration of the IEM (top rows) and Oh model (bottom row). Diamond symbols indicate the population of fitting parameters L_{opt} , with numbers indicating the local incidence angle. The mean fitted function $L_{opt} = f(rms)$ (using all data) is shown as a thick black line, while thin gray lines corresponds to the individual fittings of the 30 “bootstrap” re-samples of the original data. The top-right textbox in each panel provides the equation of the mean fitted function and its coefficients (with 95% confidence intervals corresponding to the “bootstrap” in brackets), as well as the determination coefficient (r_{adj}^2 , adjusted for sample size) and rmse of the mean fitted function. Also shown are the calibration functions by [22] and [9] for various C-band and L-band configurations, the fitting parameter L_{opt} optimised in [9] for L-band SIR-C data (gray dots) and the calibration function fitted in this study to the SIR-C data (L-HH-44-57).

